

Powdered activated mustard cake (PAMC) : Synthesis, characterization and its use for aqueous phase adsorption of phenolics

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Abstract : The powdered activated mustard cake (PAMC) from mustard oil cake was derived and characterized for selective adsorption of phenolics. The pore distribution lay in between macroporous and mesoporous domains. The BET surface area of the PAMC was typically found as $S_{\text{BET}} = 26 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The adsorption properties of studied phenolic acids depended on several factors such as pK_a , functional group present, polarity, molecular weight, size and solution condition such as pH, ionic strength and adsorbed concentration. Adsorption decreased with increase of pH of adsorbate solution. The adsorption coefficient for the studied phenolics followed the sequence : *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid > chlorogenic acid > 7-hydroxycoumarin > syringic acid > *p*-coumaric acid. Adsorption was found to increase markedly with increase in ionic strength from 0.20 to 0.12 M suggesting a role for the hydrophobic force in this adsorption process. Adsorption was reduced substantially by the addition of urea; therefore, hydrogen bonding appeared to play an important role in this adsorption process. In the present case, adsorption was found to be reversible in nature. Thus, the observed adsorption appeared to be a complex interplay of hydrophobic, electrostatic and dispersive interactions.

Keywords : Powdered activated mustard cake (PAMC), adsorption, phenolic acids.

Introduction

Adsorption of phenols and their derivatives (water contaminants) from aqueous solutions on carbon is one of the most studied areas¹⁻¹⁹ of all liquid-phase applications of carbon adsorbents. However, there is a dearth of such investigation of anti-oxidant-polyphenolic compounds on other adsorbents. Polyphenols including flavonoids and phenolic acids are products of the secondary metabolism of plants. In plants, polyphenols may act as phytoalexins, antifeedants, and attractants for pollinators, contributors to plant pigmentation, and protective agents against UV light²⁰. In addition, polyphenols exhibit many biological properties such as anticarcinogenic, anti-ulcer, antithrombotic, anti-inflammatory, immune modulating, anti-allergic, antimicrobial, vasodilatory, and antioxidant activities²¹. Polyphenols have become an intense focus of research because

of their perceived health-beneficial effects.

Phenolic acids are widely distributed in sugarcane and are color precursors in cane sugar manufacture^{22,23}. Phenolic acids have significant biological and pharmacological properties, some of which were shown to be effective in preventing cancer²⁴. They contribute to color formation of juice when sugar cane is crushed, are also involved in the changes that take place during the processing of sugarcane for the production of raw sugar^{25,26}. In the present contribution, we report the adsorption behavior of phenolic acids onto PAMC; a new adsorbent derived from agricultural waste (mustard oil cake). The chlorogenic acid, *p*-coumaric acid, *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, 7-hydroxycoumarin and syringic acid were chosen as representative phenolics which are commonly found in plants particularly in sugar cane. The basic information concerning phenolic compounds is tabulated in Table 1.

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Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of the studied phenolics compounds

Phenolic compound	Melting point (°C)	pK _a at 25 °C	Aqueous solubility at 25 °C (g/100 ml)	Density (g/cm ³)	Surface tension (dyne/cm)
 Chlorogenic acid	208	pK _a = 7.8	Slightly soluble	1.28	101.9
 <i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	206	pK _{a₁} = 4.36 pK _{a₂} = 8.98	Slightly soluble	1.33	62.42
 <i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	214	pK _{a₁} = 4.48 pK _{a₂} = 9.32	0.2	1.46	64.41
 7-Hydroxycoumarin	226	pK _a = 9.16	1.0	1.40	59.49
 Syringic acid	207	pK _{a₁} = 4.71 pK _{a₂} = 9.12	0.58	1.33	51.61

Experimental

Polyphenolics were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. The PAMC derived from an inexpensive, abundantly available and eco-friendly source^{27,28} was used as absorbent.

Synthesis of the PAMC : The mustard oil cake (after extraction of oil) primarily consists of carbohydrates and proteins^{27,28}. The de-oiled mustard cake (DOMC) samples were taken from a local oil mill and was crushed to powder in a mortar-pastle . The material was washed several times with distilled water till colorless and then sundried.

The DOMC was then treated with H₂O₂ at 60 °C for 24 h to oxidize the adhering organic matter. The resulting material was further washed several times using double distilled water. The powder was dried at 110 °C for 24 h and it was then burnt in Muffle furnace at 715 °C for 25 min in the absence of air passing nitrogen gas. Finally the material was ground and passed through a 100 mesh sieve and stored in desiccators.

Methodology : Stock solutions of phenolic acids (1000 ppm) were prepared by dissolving appropriate amounts.

Standard solutions were prepared by further dilution of stock solutions. A 3 ml aliquot of the diluted phenolic acid was transferred to a test tube containing 5.5 ml distilled water. After mixing the contents, Folin-Ciocalteu phenol (FCP) reagent (0.5 ml) was added and shaken thoroughly. 1 ml of saturated Na₂CO₃ solution was added and mixed thoroughly and filtered (0.45 μm). The absorbance of this solution was determined at λ_{max} 736 nm against water plus reagent blank by UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Double beam UV 5704SS). The residual phenolic acid concentration was measured (λ_{max} = 736 nm) using the standard curve.

Characterization of PAMC :

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy : The PAMC (2 mg) was mixed with 200 mg of KBr and then pelletized. The FT-IR spectra of the pellets were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer Precisely FT-IR spectrophotometer (model Spectrum BX).

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) : The particle morphologies of the PAMC were studied using scanning electron microscope (LEO 430, Cambridge, UK). Samples were mounted on aluminum stab with the help of double-sided tape. Mounted stabs were coated with gold palladium prior to analysis using a Polaron sputter coater.

N₂ and H₂ adsorption : Nitrogen and hydrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms were recorded using a Beckmann Coulter SA 3100 surface area analyzer at 77 K. Prior to the measurements, all the samples were degassed at 398 K for 4 h.

Point of zero charge (PZC) for PAMC : The PZC characteristic of PAMC was determined by solid addition method using 0.1 M KCl and 0.002 M citrimide (C₁₉H₄₂BrN) solutions. 40 ml of KCl and citrimide solution was taken in 100 ml Stoppered conical flask. The initial pH values of the solutions were roughly adjusted between 2 and 12 by adding either 0.1 N HCl or 0.1 N NaOH. The total volume of the solution in each flask was adjusted exactly to 50 ml by adding the KCl and citrimide solution. The initial pH of the solution was then accurately noted. 0.5 g of PAMC was added to each flask. The suspensions were shaken and allowed to equilibrate for two days with intermittent shaking. The final pH values of the supernatant liquid were noted. The difference between the initial and final pH values (ΔpH = pH_i -

pH_f) were plotted against the initial pH value. The point of intersection of the resulting curve at which change in pH is zero, gives the PZC value.

Physico-chemical and adsorption characteristics of PAMC : The physico-chemical properties (Bulk density, hardness, pH and mineral content), and adsorption properties (Iodine and molasses tests) of the PAMC were examined.

Iodine test : The percent iodine removed (PIR) by PAMC and reference carbon (activated charcoal, Darco G-60, 100 mesh powder) was calculated using following equation :

$$\text{PIR} = \frac{\text{ml thiosulphate used for blank} - \text{ml thiosulphate used for sample}}{\text{ml thiosulphate used for blank}} \times 100$$

Molasses test : A solution of final molasses was treated with the PAMC and the reference carbon of known molasses number. The filtrate absorbances were measured and molasses number of the sample was evaluated from the ratio of the absorbance values of the sample and the reference carbon.

The percent molasses color removed (PMCR) was evaluated as follows :

$$\text{PMCR} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of blank} - \text{Absorbance of PAMC treated sample}}{\text{Absorbance of blank}} \times 100$$

Triplicate analysis of a sample was performed Standard deviation and standard error in each case was evaluated using the following formulae :

$$\text{Standard deviation (S)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

$$\text{Standard error} = \frac{S}{\sqrt{n}}$$

where, *n* is total number of samples, \bar{x} is average of samples and *x* is value of each sample.

Results and discussion

Physical properties of the PAMC : The adsorbent derived from DOMC looks like light gray amorphous solid. The physical properties of PAMC are tabulated in Table 2.

Table 2. Physical properties of PAMC

Bulk density (g/ml)	Hardness	Conductivity (μ S)	pH	Ash content (% dry weight)
0.862 ± 0.005	78.30 ± 0.5	291.60 ± 50	8.81 ± 0.05	6.99 ± 0.05

\pm indicates standard error.

Iodine test and molasses test : The Iodine Number (IN)²⁹ is a relative indicator of porosity in activated carbons. For high surface area carbons (greater than 900 m²/g), iodine number is numerically similar to BET surface area measurements, whereas for low surface area active carbons, this one-to-one correlation of surface area with IN falls away. The results (Table 3) consistent with this statement are observed in the present case.

The molasses test²⁹ results are shown in the Table 3. A solution of final molasses was treated with the PAMC and the reference carbon of known molasses number. The filtrate absorbance values were measured and molasses number of the sample was evaluated from the ratio of the absorbance values of the sample and the reference carbon.

Chemical composition of the PAMC : The PAMC was analyzed for its chemical composition. The chemical composition of PAMC is tabulated in Table 4.

FT-IR spectroscopy : Fig. 1 illustrates several bands of FT-IR spectra. The absorption band around 876 cm⁻¹ is due to Si-OH bond stretching which reveal that the condensation of Si-OH groups was not complete on thermal treatment. The typical absorption band for Si-O-Si network vibrations were observed at 1040 cm⁻¹ and 876 cm⁻¹ and the absorption band at 1040 cm⁻¹ increases with increase of SiO₂ content. Bands at 3464 cm⁻¹ to 3723 cm⁻¹ are due to the chemisorbed water and surface hydroxyl groups³⁰⁻³². The band at 476 cm⁻¹ belongs to O-Si-O bending vibration³³. Some of the others bands originating from the sample are characteristics of -OH stretching (3454 cm⁻¹). The FT-IR spectra clearly demonstrate that PAMC contain mainly silica. The FT-IR spectra of the PAMC after syringic acid adsorption is shown in Fig. 2 which shows an adsorption band near at 3389.4 cm⁻¹ attributed to -OH groups. The absorption band at 1370 cm⁻¹ indicates O-H rather than C-H or C-C

Table 3. Comparative adsorption properties of PAMC with activated charcoal (reference)

Sl. No.	Amount of adsorbent (g)	Percent iodine removed (PIR)		Percent molasses color removed (PMCR)	
		PAMC ($S_{\text{BET}} = 26 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$)	Activated charcoal ($S_{\text{BET}} = 1043 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$)	PAMC	Activated charcoal
1.	0.1	12	42 ± 1.5	-	37 ± 1.0
2.	0.2	18	60 ± 2.0	3.4	50 ± 1.6
3.	0.3	24 ± 1	85 ± 2.0	5.8	77 ± 2.0
4.	0.4	27 ± 1	94 ± 2.0	7.4	90 ± 2.0
5.	0.5	29 ± 1	97 ± 2.0	10.0	95 ± 2.0

Table 4. Chemical composition of the PAMC

Component	%
C	6.33
H	1.37
N	0.56
S	0.11
SiO ₂	35.00
Al ₂ O ₃	0.26
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.28
CaO	30.66
MgO	7.85

bond. The occurrence of some new peaks and masking of some peaks after the adsorption confirms the uptake of phenolic acids.

SEM characterization : The SEM images of PAMC shown in Fig. 3 clearly demonstrate the porosity and surface texture of new adsorbent material.

BET characterization : According to Dabrowski³⁴, a typical definition of pore diameter ranges is as follows : micropores, <2 nm; mesopores, 2-50 nm; macropores, >50 nm. Fig. 4 shows N₂/H₂ adsorption/desorption iso-

Fig. 1. FT-IR spectrum of PAMC (100 mesh).

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectrum of PAMC (100 mesh) after adsorption of syringic acid.

Fig. 3. SEM images of PAMC (100 mesh) at different magnifications.

Fig. 4. N₂ isotherm and pore size distribution of PAMC from N₂ adsorption data.

therms of the PAMC at 77 K. The hysteresis that appears as the difference in the two curves at $p/p_0 > 0.7$ is due to N₂ condensation, a typical phenomenon shown by mesoporous materials. Fig. 4 illustrates pore size distribution of which clearly shows that microporous are absent. In the mesoporous domain, the pore radii range between 2–30 nm with a maximum at about 20–35 nm. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) specific surface area (S_{BET}) is typically 26 m² g⁻¹ N₂ adsorption allows relatively an accurate characterization over the mesoporous to microporous domain³⁵. The calculations were in agreement with the cylindrical pore model for the mercury intrusion porosimetry and the BET³⁶ for surface area and Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) (pore distribution) model³⁷ for N₂ adsorption isotherms.

PZC characterization : The surface potential of the adsorbent may be influenced by the pH value of the co-existing liquid bulk phase. Fig. 5 illustrate that pH_{PZC} of PAMC was found to be about 9.8. The pH value, at

Fig. 5. Point of zero charge (PZC) of PAMC by solid addition method.

which the surface charge is zero, is called the point of zero charge (PZC). The surface is positively charged at $pH < pH_{PZC}$ and negatively charged at $pH > pH_{PZC}$. Since, pH_{PZC} of the PAMC was determined and found to be about 9.8, at any $pH < pH_{PZC}$, the surface of PAMC is positively charged and at $pH > pH_{PZC}$, the surface is negative.

Adsorption isotherms :

Accordingly Giles *et al.*³⁸ classification the titled adsorbate-adsorbent system illustrates L₂ type of adsorption.

Influence of concentration and adsorption isotherm :

The influence of increasing concentration of phenolics acids on adsorption has been investigated by varying in the range of 1.0 to 6.0 × 10⁻⁵ mol/L. The result shown in Fig. 6 illustrates that the amount of adsorption increases with increasing concentration of phenolics solution and finally becomes constant. This is due to fact that

Fig. 6. Adsorption behavior of phenolic acids onto PAMC at different concentration.

Fig. 7. Effect of contact time for the adsorption of phenolic acid by PAMC.

Fig. 8. Adsorption behavior of phenolic acids onto PAMC at different adsorbent dosage.

on increasing the concentration of phenolic acids, the availability of phenolics molecules at the interface increases which in turn enhance the amount of adsorption. Finally when all the available sites on the adsorbent surface are occupied, it becomes difficult for phenolics acids to interact with the PAMC surface resulting in saturated adsorption. Adsorption isotherms shown in Figs. 6–8 illustrate that in the present case the adsorption isotherm resembles with a typical Langmuirian plot (L_2 -type) indicating that the adsorption process follows Langmuir equation.

Adsorption coefficients ($K = k_1/k_2$) :

Adsorption coefficient K was evaluated using the well-known Langmuir's equation

$$a = \frac{KC_e a_s}{1 + KC_e}$$

$$1 + KC_e = KC_e \frac{a_s}{a}$$

or

$$\frac{C_e}{a} = \frac{1}{a_s K} + \frac{C_e}{a_s} \quad (1)$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate, K is the adsorption coefficient, a and a_s is the adsorbed amount of adsorbate (mg g^{-1} at equilibrium and at saturation, respectively). The ratio of slope to intercept of the linear plots (Figures not shown) so obtained gives the value for the adsorption coefficient. The adsorption coefficient for the studied phenolics follows the sequence : *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid > chlorogenic acid > 7-hydroxycoumarin > syringic acid > *p*-coumaric acid. It was concluded that hydroxyl and carboxyl groups increases the adsorption of the phenolic acids.

Kinetics of adsorption :

Adsorption kinetics was studied monitoring the progress of the adsorption process at different time intervals and the rate of adsorption was found to be almost constant up to nearly 90 min (Fig. 7) it then decreased gradually with time and finally attained a constant value near 120 min. Thus, from the constant rate region^{39,40} the rate constant for adsorption (k_1) and desorption (k_2), may be calculated using Langmuir's isotherm equation, according to which the rate of adsorption (R_{ad}) is given by

$$R_{ad} = k_1 C (1 - \theta) - k_2 \theta \quad (2)$$

where k_1 , k_2 , C and θ have their usual significance. Now, in order to calculate the rate constant for adsorption (k_1), the following assumption can be adopted :

(i) The rate of adsorption may be approximated by the rate of decrease in concentration of the adsorbate solution; i.e.

$$R_{ad} = -dC/dt \quad (3)$$

(ii) In the initial (obviously linear) portion of the adsorbed amount versus time curve, the rate of desorption may be neglected as the adsorption is dominant in the initial periods, i.e. $k_2 \ll k_1$, and, as a consequence, the second term on the right hand side of eq. (2) can be ignored in comparison to the first term; i.e. $k_1 C(1 - \theta) > k_2 \theta$.

(iii) The surface coverage (θ) may approximate as

$$\theta = q(t)/q_{eq} = (C_0 - C)/(C_0 - C_e) \quad (4)$$

where $q(t)$ and q_{eq} are the amount adsorbed at time t and

at equilibrium and C_0 is the initial bulk concentration of adsorbate solutions. Thus, following the above simplification, we can write eq. as

$$-\frac{dc}{dt} = k_1 C \frac{C - C_e}{C_0 - C} \quad (5)$$

If equilibrium adsorption arrives at a much later stage then the numerical value of C_e may be ignored in comparison to those of C_0 and C (as approximation), and eq. (5) is reduced to

$$-\frac{dc}{C^2} = k_1 \frac{dt}{C_0} \quad (6)$$

Upon complete integration of eq. (6), we get

$$\frac{1}{C} = \frac{k_1}{C_0} t + \frac{1}{C_0} \quad (7)$$

where C is the concentration of adsorbate solution at any time t , C_0 is initial concentration of adsorbate.

The adsorption coefficient (K) was first calculated by using the linearized Langmuir equation (1). The ratio of the slope to the intercept of the linear plots between C_e and C_e/a (Figure not shown) also furnishes the numerical values of the adsorption coefficients. Obviously, from the plot between $1/C$ and t , the value of k_1 may be calculated using eq. (7). Once k_1 is known, the value of k_2 may be found, since k_1/k_2 has already been evaluated by eq. (1). Many other investigators^{41,42} also used the value of K as (k_1/k_2) , as adopted in the present study. The superiority of this method for evaluating the kinetic parameters lies in the fact that no complicated mathematical computations⁴³ (such as in the Runge-Kutta method or Marquardt routine) are required and a simple linear plot will serve the purpose well. The adsorption and kinetics parameters for the adsorption of the examined phenolics onto PAMC surface are summarized in Table 5.

Effect of surface functionalities and pH of solution :

It has been reported^{44,45} that in solution, phenolics behave as weak acids :

The initial pH of adsorption medium is one of the most

Table 5. Adsorption parameters of phenolic acids onto PAMC

Phenolic acids	K_1	K_2	Adsorption coefficient ($L \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Adsorption capacity	
				Experimental (mg/g)	Graphical (mg/g)
Chlorogenic acid	3.0×10^5	2.4	2.0×10^5	1.8	2.0
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	1.0×10^6	2.0	5.0×10^5	1.7	2.0
Syringic acid	1.5×10^5	2.0	1.0×10^5	1.5	1.6
<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	0.1×10^5	5.0	1.0×10^5	1.0	1.3
7-Hydroxycoumarin	3.0×10^5	2.5	1.2×10^5	1.0	1.3

important parameters affecting the adsorption process. Fig. 9 shows the effect of pH on the adsorption of phenolics and adsorption was found to decrease with increasing pH. The pH primarily affects the degree of ionization of phenolics and the surface properties of the PAMC. At low pH values, the surface of the PAMC would be proto-

The effect of pH can also be explained using pH_{PZC} of the adsorbent. In the present study the pH_{PZC} of PAMC is 9.8. At any pH below pH_{PZC} , the surface of the PAMC is positively charged and at pH above pH_{PZC} , the surface is negative. When the solution pH is lowered than pH_{PZC} , the phenolate ions are more easily attracted by the posi-

Fig. 9. Adsorption behavior of phenolic acids onto PAMC at different pH values.

nated and resulted in a stronger attraction for negatively charged phenolate ions. At high pH, OH^- ions would compete with the phenolic molecules for sorption sites. Sorption of excess of OH^- ions could convert an initial positively charged surface of the PAMC into a negatively charged surface resulting repulsion of negatively charged phenolate ions and thus adsorption decreased⁴⁶. This could also be due to the increased solubility of phenolic molecules in alkaline conditions, which results in greater affinity for the phenolic molecules to remain in solution rather than to get adsorbed onto the PAMC surface. Un-ionized phenolic molecules would also be attracted, possibly, by physical force (H-bonding).

tively charged surface of the PAMC, favouring accumulation of phenolate ions on the surface and thus promoting adsorption. On the other hand, when the solution pH exceeded pH_{PZC} , the phenolate ions are repelled by the negative charged surface of the PAMC, hence, adsorption was found to decrease.

Thermodynamics of titled adsorbate-adsorbent system :
The effect of temperature on the adsorption behavior of PAMC has been studied in the range of 30–50 °C. Fig. 10 demonstrate an endothermic nature of the process. Thermodynamic parameters were calculated as follows :

(i) ΔG^0 was calculated using the equation $\Delta G^0 =$

Fig. 10. Adsorption isotherms showing influence of temperature on adsorption of phenolics onto PAMC.

$-2.303 RT \log b$, where b is the Langmuir constant at temperature 27 °C. Langmuir isotherm is commonly used for the sorption of a variety of compounds, and the linear form of this isotherm is given by the following equation: $1/q_e = 1/Q_0 + 1/bQ_e C_e$, where q_e is the amount adsorbed (mg/g), C is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (mg/L) and Q_0 and b are the Langmuir constants related to maximum adsorption capacity and energy of adsorption, respectively. When $1/q_e$ was plotted against $1/C_e$ straight lines with slope $1/bC_e$ were obtained.

(ii) Apparent heat of adsorption enthalpy, ΔH^0 was evaluated using the equation

$$2.303R \log b_2/b_1 = \Delta H^0 (1/T_1 - 1/T_2)$$

(iii) Entropy, ΔS^0 was estimated using the equation $\Delta G^0 = \Delta H^0 - T\Delta S^0$

The endothermic nature of the adsorption was confirmed by the thermodynamic parameters as shown in Table 6. The negative value of ΔG^0 is an indication of spontaneous nature of the process. Apparent enthalpy of

Table 6. Thermodynamic parameters for adsorption of phenolic acids onto PAMC surface at 27 °C

Phenolic acids	$-\Delta G^0$ (kcal/mol)	$-\Delta H^0$ (kcal/mol)	$-\Delta S^0$ (cal/mol K)
Cholorogenic acid	1.01	6.97	0.026
Syringic acid	1.02	6.69	0.025
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.83	7.35	0.027
7-Hydroxycoumarin	1.0	7.30	0.027
<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	1.12	5.98	0.023

adsorption, ΔH^0 also confirms the endothermic nature of the adsorption process.

Adsorption mechanism: The adsorption mechanism is postulated on the basis of the nature of oxygen surface functionalities and the surface charge of the PAMC. Thus, the charge-transfer mechanism and inter ionic attractions seem to be responsible for the adsorption process. Our assumption is based on the following observations:

It is suggested that the phenolic compounds present in solution adsorb on PAMC surface by a donor-acceptor complex mechanism involving the surface oxygen of the PAMC acting as electron donor and aromatic ring of the phenolics as the acceptor. The FT-IR spectrum of the PAMC shown in Fig. 1 reveals the presence of the oxygen groups ($1435, 1045 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which give assurance in favour of the purposed mechanism. The purposed mechanism is also consistent with the literature model⁴⁷. Previous studies have proposed that the adsorption of phenolic compounds on oxygen surface is mainly determined by dispersive, hydrogen-bonding and electrostatic interactions between the adsorbate and adsorbent, and the surface area and the porosity of the adsorbent⁴⁸.

Since PZC of the PAMC has been found 9.8 which is very close to the pK_a values of the aforesaid polyphenolics⁴⁹. The neutral form of phenolics is preferentially adsorbed on the surface of the ashes. The dispersive interaction is considered to be the predominant mechanism for phenolic adsorption by the ashes as silica which is expected

to be highly hydrophilic and is therefore unlikely to contribute to phenolics adsorption⁴⁹. The dispersive interaction occurs between the ring of phenolics and aromatic moieties of the ash⁵⁰.

The oxygen-containing functional groups provide H-bonding sites for the neutral species of phenolics as well as for adsorbed water. The -OH groups of phenolics can be partially bound to the surface through H-bonding to the oxygen containing functional groups. However, the same binding sites, there is a possibility of H-bond formation, which will hinder phenolics adsorption by reducing the binding sites and the accessible surface area by blocking smaller pores^{51,52}. Comparatively, stronger H-bonding strength of water, the contribution of H-bonding sites provided by oxygen containing functional groups can be insignificant for phenolics adsorption compared to the contribution of dispersive interactions.

Effect of urea on adsorption :

To explore the role of hydrogen bonding, adsorption tests were carried out in the presence of urea, a hydrogen bond breaker and results are shown in Fig. 11. Adsorption was reduced markedly in the presence of urea. Therefore, it is proposed that hydrogen bonding plays an important role in the adsorption of studied phenolics onto the PAMC.

Effect of ionic strength :

The influence of the ionic strength on the adsorption was investigated by adding different salts in the concentration range 0.02–0.12 M. If hydrophobic forces make a significant contribution to adsorption, the adsorption density would have increased with the addition of salt due to salting out effect⁵³. The results shown in Fig. 12 clearly demonstrate that amount of adsorbed phenolics increases with increasing ionic strength suggesting the role of hydrophobic force for the observed adsorption and obeys the sequence; $\text{Cl}^- < \text{SO}_4^{2-} < \text{PO}_4^{3-}$. Similarly, the cations were added in the same concentration range as anions and the effectiveness was found to obey the sequence; $\text{Na}^+ < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Fe}^{3+}$. Chlorogenic acid was chosen as a representative phenolic under study.

Reversible adsorption of phenolic acids : In the present case, adsorption of phenolic acids onto PAMC was found to be reversible in nature, although the recovery was found in the range of 10–20%. However, adsorption of phenols and its derivatives (contaminants) have been reported as irreversible and weakly adsorbed, i.e. physisorbed phenol can become chemisorbed in the course of time or by increasing the temperature on commercial activated carbon and the chemisorptions is inhibited by the presence of oxygen surface complexes^{54,55}. The reversible adsorbed

Fig. 11. Adsorption isotherms of phenolics on PAMC with and without urea.

Fig. 12. Plots showing influence of ionic strength on adsorption of chlorogenic acid onto PAMC.

phenolic acids were extracted by double distilled water, and the extracted solution were analyzed by UV-spectrophotometry employing the procedure of color development as used in the estimation of studied individual phenolic acids. The recovery of phenolics from PAMC surface has been summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Recovery of phenolics from PAMC

Phenolics	Amount loaded (mg)	Amount adsorbed (mg)	% Adsorption	Adsorbate recovery (%)
Chlorogenic acid	0.5	0.220	44	17
Syringic acid	0.5	0.265	53	14
<i>p</i> -Coumaric acid	0.5	0.220	44	12
7-Hydroxycoumarin	0.5	0.205	41	10
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic acid	0.5	0.335	67	21

Conclusions

The PAMC; derived from mustard oil cake has great potential for the removal of the phenolics. The adsorption properties of studied phenolic acids depends on several factors such as pK_a value, functional group present, polarity, molecular weight, size and preparatory condition such as pH, ionic strength and adsorbate concentration. Since, the pH_{PZC} of the PAMC is determined as 9.8, therefore, at any pH below pH_{PZC} , the surface of adsorbent is positively charged and at pH above pH_{PZC} , the surface is negative. When the solution pH is lowered

than pH_{PZC} , the phenolate ions are more easily attracted by the positively charged surface of adsorbent, favouring accumulation of phenolate ions on the surface and thus promoting adsorption. On the other hand, when the solution pH exceeded pH_{PZC} , the phenolate ions are repelled by the negative charged surface of adsorbent, hence, adsorption is decreased. It is suggested that the phenolic compounds present in solution adsorb on PAMC surface by a donor-acceptor complex mechanism involving the surface oxygen of the PAMC acting as electron donor and aromatic ring of the phenolics as the acceptor. The FT-IR spectrum of the PAMC shows the presence of the oxygen groups ($1435, 1045\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which supports the proposed mechanism. The proposed mechanism is also consistent with the literature available. In addition, this adsorption process is a complex interplay of electrostatics and dispersive interactions.

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